

Digitalizing the Forest-Wood Chain: Implementation of the TRESTIMA App for Douglas Fir in Italy

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ABSTRACT

Collecting qualitative and quantitative forest data is essential for effective and sustainable forest management and planning. Information on species composition, tree density, basal area, and wood volume per hectare, as well as data describing stand wood quality, is crucial to help forest owners and managers define clear planning objectives and develop efficient strategies to achieve them. However, traditional data collection is often costly and time-consuming. To accelerate the process, without compromising reliability, modernizing the technological landscape of the forest-wood supply chain is essential for the whole forest-wood supply chain.

In this context, the Horizon Project *DigiMedFor* aims to enhance competitiveness and promote the sustainable management of Mediterranean forests by, among other initiatives, implementing quick and easy-to-use tools for forest inventory and tree quality assessment.

TRESTIMA is a mobile application that analyzes pictures taken with a smartphone while walking through the forest. Using image analysis techniques, tree stems are segmented, wooden species are identified, and stem diameters are measured. The application generates reports on basal area, diameter distribution, tree height, and volumes. Initially developed in the Nordic countries, TRESTIMA was adapted for use in the Mediterranean environments as part of the *DigiMedFor* project. Four key implementations were done: improved species detection; algorithm corrections to account for steep terrain; adjustments for high basal area stands (exceeding 50 m²/ha), and trees with a diameter at breast height over 40 cm; and the development and implementation of a stem quality index for standing trees.

In central Italy, 31 Douglas fir forest compartments were sampled, with an average of 15 pictures taken per compartment using the mobile application. A visually assessed stem quality index (ranging from 1 to 3, with 1 being the highest quality) was developed and assigned to each compartment by expert evaluators. Applying machine learning and computer vision techniques, the collected images were used to train the app for species detection and assessment of stem quality.

Additionally, 20 of these compartments were surveyed using traditional forest inventory methods (diameter and height measurements via caliper and hypsometer) in circular sample plots, serving as reference data for algorithm calibration.

As a result, the species detection rate reached 83%, and an accuracy of 71% was achieved for stem quality index classification. Forest inventory metrics showed consistent accuracy, with a correlation of $r = 0.88$ between app estimates and reference data for stand basal area. These enhancements make the application an efficient and reliable digital tool for forest surveys and inventory, with further improvements expected as more data become available through continued use.

KEYWORDS: forest inventory, image analysis, machine learning, Mediterranean forests